
Millennial Fathers' Perceptions of Fatherhood: Insights from Bapak2ID on Instagram as Reference Group

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ABSTRACT: Modern fathers have shifted from traditional views, where paternal figures were seen solely as providers and authoritarian figures with limited emotional engagement in their children's lives, to becoming more involved and authoritative. This shift has been influenced by the rise of the internet and social media, which emphasize the importance of paternal figures in a child's development. It has also reshaped fathers' perceptions of themselves as positive role models who actively and emotionally engage with their children. Millennial fathers in Indonesia, accustomed to accessing information and communicating through social media, have integrated these platforms into their daily lives. While parenting resources often prioritize the maternal role, Bapak2ID bridges this gap by offering a platform where millennial fathers can acquire knowledge, share information, and discuss topics related to fatherhood and parenting. This study employs a qualitative approach to analyze the comments of male followers on Bapak2ID's 22 content posts over a three-month period (September to November 2024). These selected posts highlight topics on fatherhood and examine how followers process the messages, whether through central, peripheral routes, or combination of both routes and to connect it to their perception on fatherhood in their daily lives.

KEYWORDS: father, millennial, paternal, fatherhood, parenting, authoritative figure, social media, reference group

I. INTRODUCTION

In traditional views, fathers are often perceived as "authority figures, breadwinners, and emotionally distant" (Ammari & Schoenebeck, 2015, p.1906). This perception limits appreciation of fathers' roles to their financial contributions rather than emotional engagement (Yunianti et al., 2023). Many modern fathers still tend to replicate the parenting styles they experienced in childhood, often without critical examination. This inclination persists even when these inherited approaches may not fully support healthy child development, reflecting the lasting impact of generational parenting practices. These inherited approaches may persist even when they do not necessarily support or encourage healthy child development, highlighting the generational influence on parenting practices. Despite evolving societal norms, parents often lack the awareness and skills needed to adapt to more egalitarian parenting approaches. In Indonesia, deep-rooted patriarchal norms reinforce traditional roles, viewing men as primary economic providers and women as primary caregivers, with "parenting" still commonly associated with mothers. However, research shows that a child's social, mental, and intellectual development depends on the involvement of both parents. Hidayah et al. (2023) found that fatherlessness can lead to negative psychological effects in children, such as low self-esteem, poor emotional control, and a lack of ambition and assertiveness.

Studies show that positive father involvement significantly contributes to children's development. Fathers who actively engage in parenting, provide financial support, and spend quality time with their children contribute to fostering high self-esteem, along with strong social and cognitive skills in their children (Hidayati et al., 2011; Hidayah et al., 2023). This raises an essential question: How does digital communication, particularly social media, help fathers shift from limited involvement to more active caregiving roles?

The internet and social media have profoundly transformed how millennial parents communicate and access information. In Indonesia, social media usage is notably high, with men making up 53.5% of users, and a large segment of male users aged 25–44 (We Are Social, 2024). Social media has redefined everyday interactions, enabling individuals and organizations to engage widely across platforms (Freberg, 2019) and creating a larger network of interconnected communities tied together through virtual and offline connections. For millennial fathers, these online support systems are pivotal in shifting traditional parenting roles toward more egalitarian perspectives, motivating fathers to engage actively in caregiving.

Despite the higher number of male social media users, men encounter gender-based disparities in parenting resources online, as social media strongly emphasizes maternal roles, making parenting seem largely associated with motherhood. The abundant information tailored to mothers at various life stages—pregnancy to teenage parenting—highlights the gap in resources

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for fathers as if they were secondary caregivers. This underrepresentation of fathers on social media contributes to a narrative that marginalizes their role, often rendering them invisible in the parenting process. As a result, fathers may feel undervalued and question their significance in childcare (Pierre, 2024).

Living within social groups means that individuals are consistently influenced by collective values, behavioral norms, and the quality of their relationships, which shapes their consumption choices and makes group influence essential in adopting new social norms. Social media, now a central part of everyday life, supports these social needs by enabling individuals to connect, learn, and document their experiences. For fathers, in particular, social media provides a vital platform for peer support, access to fathers to navigate perceived judgment and stigma, privacy concerns, and anonymity needs, creating a “safe space” for open discussion without fear of criticism. A digital report by We Are Social (2024) indicates that primary motivations for social media use include connecting with like-minded communities (30.9%) and sharing opinions (28.9%), highlighting the platform’s value in building supportive networks among fathers.

Within the social media realm, various platforms allow users to engage and interact freely, resulting in rich discussions and exchanges of ideas. These interactions help shape and influence individual behaviors, as people may often feel an indirect pressure to meet their social group’s expectations. As Nimmerman (2019) observes, individuals frequently adapt their behavior to align with their reference groups, such as peer groups. In social media, where behavior and attitudes can be shared and observed widely, reference groups—defined by family, social class, culture, and subculture—have significant influence. These groups serve as benchmarks, influencing values, opinions, and behaviors as users interact with and learn from one another (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019).

Bapak2ID exemplifies how reference groups can engage millennial fathers seeking guidance across various life dimensions, especially fatherhood. The group offers practical, relatable advice and models positive parenting without projecting an air of superiority, creating a supportive, judgment-free environment. Bapak2ID promotes the idea that positive values easily influence men and can significantly impact their communities (Kasisolusi, 2022; Josua, n.d.). Through humor or “dad jokes,” the group provides an accessible space for fathers to absorb parenting insights comfortably. Its primary goal is to share actionable “do’s and don’ts” for fathers or husbands, and encourage younger fathers to embrace positive values while respecting diverse parenting styles (Shaffansyah, 2021, August 20).

Image 1. “Dads, what will be your response if suddenly your little girl who’s still in Elementary said “A boy at school has a crush on me” (Bapak2ID, 2024)

Image 2. "Daddy's home!" (Bapak2ID, 2024)

Image 3. "Father's love languages that his children often misinterpret" (Bapak2ID, 2024)

Bapak2ID incorporates fatherhood-related content as one of its primary topics and content pillars on Instagram. Each month, they consistently post content designed to engage and guide middle-aged male followers in their roles as fathers and parents. This content is delivered through various formats, including question-based posts, prayers, reflections, quizzes, graphic illustrations, and practical tips. These posts aim to foster engagement and provide insights into fatherhood.

The three images referenced above, posted between September and November 2024, exemplify the platform's approach to addressing fathers' concerns, affections, and misunderstood actions by their children. The first image, shared on September 6, 2024, seeks to initiate conversations and gather followers' perspectives on how they would react if male classmates admired their daughters. This post encourages reflection and dialogue on paternal attitudes and expectations towards challenging issues. The second image, posted on October 8, 2024, portrays the emotional connection between a father and his daughter. It highlights the shared longing they experience while apart, emphasizing the joy and fulfillment of reuniting after a day's work. This post illustrates the deep bond in a father-daughter relationship. Then, the third image which was shared on Father's Day (November 12, 2024), explores the theme of misinterpretation of a father's love language by his children. This post sheds light on how expressions of love from fathers can be misunderstood, fostering a discussion on improving communication and mutual understanding within families. Through these posts, Bapak2ID not only shares relatable fatherhood experiences but also encourages reflection and dialogue, ultimately strengthening the connection between fathers and their children.

Previous research by Ammari and Schoenebeck (2015) highlights several challenges fathers face when seeking parenting support on social media, such as feeling judged, lacking dedicated online spaces, and struggling to balance diverse perspectives with a desire for affirmation from like-minded communities. Building on this background, the present study aims to investigate how Bapak2ID, as a reference group, influences Indonesian millennial fathers' attitudes and behaviors toward embracing a more egalitarian role in parenting. This research applies the functional approach, which examines the underlying reasons for individuals' attitudes and how aligning messaging with these motivations can shape their attitudes and actions.

This study will analyze the perceptions of Bapak2ID's millennial fathers' followers on content that poses positive parenting values and the role of fathers in children's lives. These perceptions are portrayed from followers' comments in Bapak2ID's Instagram posts which also reflect the dominant parenting style of millennial fathers. This parenting style is anchored to Diana Baumrind's psychology research in the 1960s which identified three main styles of parenting: authoritative or democratic, authoritarian, and permissive (Candelanza et al., 2021). Later in the 1980s, neglectful or uninvolved parenting was added by Eleanor Maccoby and John Martin (Jessup University, n.d.). Among other parenting styles, authoritative parenting is considered as the best parenting style as it "provides a balance between structure and independence, allowing a child to grow within reasonable boundaries and explore their abilities" (Jessup University, n.d., para. 7). This parenting style has positive effects on children, both mentally and intellectually, when they get older (Cherry, 2024).

This study would explore the type of content in Bapak2ID that most millennial fathers feel related and connected to when it comes to parenting and fatherhood. And how these contents could capture the parenting style of male paternal figures and the indication to adopt positive parenting in their daily lives as fathers to their children. Using a qualitative approach by gathering secondary data from comments on Bapak2ID's Instagram posts promoting positive parenting practices and exploring the male followers' understanding of the messages, their emotional responses, their perception of the idea/concept, and their intentions to adopt new concept of behavior. The data would then be analyzed thematically, focusing on the identification of central vs. peripheral processing strategies.

Understanding these perceptions of the father's role and figure could offer valuable insights for the new program launched in December 2024 called GATE shortened for Gerakan Ayah Teladan that will be led by the Ministry of Population and Family Development/BKKBN (BKKBN Official, 2024) and also brand marketers looking to engage millennial fathers as a primary customer segment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

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A. Previous Researches

Social media platforms, such as Reddit, provide valuable data and insights into the issues fathers face during both the antenatal and postnatal periods. According to Teague & Shatte (2018), discussions in fatherhood forums cover a wide range of topics, including "parenting practices, work-life balance, and spousal relationship issues" (p. 10). These discussions serve as an important resource for understanding the diverse experiences and challenges that fathers encounter. However, there are concerns regarding the digital portrayal of fathers, particularly in apps like the DAD App in Denmark. Research by Jensen et al. (2019) highlights how such platforms can reinforce stereotypes about masculinity and traditional gender roles. Specifically, these platforms tend to portray men as less capable than women when it comes to caregiving, perpetuating the view that mothers are better suited for this role. Furthermore, studies on the perceptions of adolescents reveal interesting gendered differences in how fathers are viewed. Kolburan et al. (2012) found that female adolescents tend to perceive their fathers as more protective than male adolescents do, while male adolescents view their fathers as less democratic compared to their female peers. This suggests that fathers may be perceived differently by their children depending on their gender, which could have implications for their role in the family dynamic.

B. Reference Groups

Reference groups significantly shape consumer behavior, heavily influencing individual decision-making. According to Solomon (2018), "humans are social animals" who seek to identify with desirable groups, a primary driver of consumption. People often favor others who appear to share their identity—even if superficial—which can impact buying decisions positively or negatively as individuals conform to perceived group expectations. First introduced by Herbert H. Hyman in 1942 and further refined in behavioral sciences, the concept of reference groups suggests that people are influenced by the behaviors and thoughts of those they compare themselves to (Fernandes & Rajesh, 2018). Schiffman & Wisenblit (2019) describe reference groups as "sources of comparison, influence, and norms for people's opinions, values, and behaviors" (p. 212), with credibility grounded in perceived expertise, trustworthiness, and believability. This theory applies to Bapak2ID, a reference group that specifically targets millennial fathers. By delivering content through a personal, relatable approach, Bapak2ID resonates with millennial fathers who perceive it as more credible than traditional, impersonal advertising. This tailored approach strengthens its influence within this demographic, aligning with the group's shared values and experiences.

With the rise of mobile technology, social media has become integral to daily communication, enabling users to create accounts, form connections, and interact with others in ways that shape their purchasing decisions. Social media platforms provide an ideal environment for reference groups to influence consumer attitudes and behaviors by quickly disseminating information, often through reviews that can reach thousands instantly. This creates a powerful electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) effect, which often has a stronger impact on consumers than traditional advertising (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019; Jin & Miao, 2018).

Social media enables interaction among people by allowing them to create, share, and exchange information and ideas within virtual communities and networks. Leveraging mobile and internet technologies, social media provides highly interactive platforms that connect individuals with shared interests, enabling them to form relationships through the co-creation, discussion, and modification of user-generated content (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019). These interactions allow consumers to discuss products, events, and experiences, amplifying both individual and collective opinions as users share and reshare content. This dynamic, collaborative environment makes social media a unique and powerful tool for electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) marketing, achieving a level of influence and reach that traditional advertising often finds challenging.

In contrast to studies examining various types of reference groups—like membership and non-membership groups and their relation to consumer purchasing (Jin & Miao, 2018)—this research focuses on Bapak2ID as a membership group. Schiffman & Wisenblit (2019) define a membership group as "a group to which a person either belongs or can join and whose values he or she adopts" (p. 213). For Bapak2ID, membership refers to millennial fathers who follow the account on Instagram and engage with its fatherhood content by liking, commenting, or sharing posts. Bapak2ID demonstrates normative influence, encouraging these fathers to adopt group norms and behaviors around parenting. This normative influence fosters a shared identity among members and can lead to high conformity to group standards, as noted by Schiffman & Wisenblit (2019). In this setting, both influencers and followers are aware of their mutual influence, reinforcing community values and creating a supportive, cohesive group identity among millennial fathers.

C. Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)

Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) is a leading theory of persuasion and attitude change. According to Griffin (2011) this theory developed by Petty and Cacioppo, suggests that people process persuasive messages through either a central or a peripheral route. In the central route, individuals systematically process information and carefully consider the arguments presented. This method is likely to produce a major positive attitude change in individuals. In contrast, the peripheral route involves heuristic processing, where individuals rely on peripheral cues such as the attractiveness of the source or emotional appeals. This route is likely to produce fragile shifts in attitude. The framework (figure 1) below describes the two routes implemented in Bapak2ID's persuasive content on fatherhood so that the male followers would adopt positive parenting to their children.

Petty and Cacioppo suggest that individuals are driven to maintain accurate attitudes, but due to the overwhelming number of

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persuasive messages, they can only evaluate a limited set of ideas. People tend to focus on elaborating ideas deeply connected to their interests or ego. When individuals have a personal investment in accepting or rejecting an idea, they are more influenced by the content of the message rather than the traits of the messenger. However, when a topic loses personal relevance, it shifts to the periphery of attention, where factors like the credibility of the source gain greater significance. Without the motivation of personal relevance, there is likely to be minimal elaboration. While messages processed through the central cognitive route are more likely to result in attitude change, most messages are evaluated through the less demanding peripheral route.

D. Subculture

Schiffman and Wisenblit (2019) define a subculture as a group within a larger society that shares specific beliefs, values, and customs rooted in common factors such as ethnicity, religion, geographic location, age, or gender. These shared characteristics distinguish subcultures from the broader culture while allowing them to coexist within it.

1. Millennial Subculture:

Millennials, or Gen Y, born between 1980 and 1996 (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019), are digital natives who rely heavily on virtual communities for information. They are accustomed to instant access to information and rely on online resources for product reviews and price comparisons, reflecting their need for immediacy in decision-making. Millennials are the last generation to experience the shift from analog to digital, giving them unique digital adaptability (Willer, 2015, June 26). Studies show that millennials are particularly influenced by reference groups on social commerce platforms, with a sense of trust playing a big part in whom they consider credible (Goldberg & Kotze, 2022). Primary reference groups for millennials include family, friends, influencers, and experts, whose opinions they trust and whose interests align with their own. Influencers are significant, as millennials perceive them as trend-savvy and current. Millennials frequently consult reference groups, especially for unfamiliar products or services, due to the trust and insight these groups provide.

2. Male Subculture:

Gender also influences consumer behavior, as men typically respond more positively to comparative, straightforward, and attribute-focused advertisements (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019). The male subculture, especially in Indonesia, is shaped by traditional norms around masculinity and patriarchy, with men often viewed primarily as financial providers rather than emotional supporters. However, evolving perceptions of fatherhood are encouraging men to take on more active caregiving roles. In navigating these changes, reference groups guide male community members, particularly around fatherhood, where groups like Bapak2ID offer relatable advice and support in a non-judgmental, approachable manner. This supportive digital environment allows men to navigate potential stigma, privacy concerns, and societal expectations, creating a safe space for open discussion and shared experiences.

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1

This study employs secondary data gathered from Bapak2ID's Instagram content posts for at least three months period, specifically between September and November 2024. During this period, Bapak2ID published a total of 277 posts, with 22 posts or 8% of their content posts dedicated to parenting and fatherhood topics. The research aims to analyze the perception of millennial fathers especially on their role and figure as fathers to their children through their comments on Bapak2ID's fatherhood-related content. The target population consists of male followers who follow the Instagram account of Bapak2ID and those who contribute to the conversations and share their perspectives related to the topics of the content. The comments analyzed focus mainly on the more substantive and appropriate replies rather than the "dad jokes" from the responses. The analysis also excludes the comments from female followers who replied to the contents quoting their husbands' shared thoughts or describing their husbands' parenting behavior. The process of central and peripheral route helps to better understand the process of persuasive messages and then followed

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by the perception on fatherhood and parenting through the lenses of the millennial fathers.

No.	Date of post	Image of Post	Caption	Resume of Post	Process persuasive messages
1	September, 6, 2024		<i>Degdegan sih</i> <i>#bapak2sharing</i> <i>#deg2anmoment</i>	<p>This post seeks to initiate conversations and gather followers' perspectives on how they would react if male classmates had a crush on their daughters.</p> <p>This post also encourages reflective responses and dialogue on fathers' attitudes and sparks discussion on expectations toward challenging issues.</p>	Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)
2	September, 12, 2024		<i>Kalo bapak bisa jalanin tips2 tadi, pasti istri bapak akan makin kagum dengan skill bapak ngurusin anak yang udah sesuai standar nyaman. Digdaya bapak di rumah makin tinggi, dan kecintaan istri ke bapak makin tak terbendung.</i>	<p>This post gives tips for fathers to soothe their newborns who usually have trouble sleeping.</p> <p>This post encourages fathers to support their spouses in raising and caring for their children. It also tries to break the negative stereotype and build a narrative that fathers could take charge as caregivers and prove they are capable of doing it.</p> <p>This is a collaboration post with Lita Hutami, a parenting fluencer.</p>	Combining central (stating arguments) and peripheral route (use an influencer)

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3	September, 14, 2024		<p><i>Teruntuk anak2ku</i></p>	<p>This post is considered a “love letter” that expresses the fathers’ love towards their children.</p> <p>This post tries to break the negative stigma around fathers who are looked at as less emotional figures and tend to repress their true feelings and emotions, especially toward their children.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (emotional appeal)</p>
4	September, 23, 2024		<p><i>Ngeri banget baca berita akhir2 ini, Yaa Allah :(</i></p> <p><i>#bapak2doasenin</i></p> <p><i>#lindungikamiyaallah</i></p> <p><i>#semangatpelindung keluarga</i></p>	<p>This post is a prayer responding to negative news (criminal cases) circulating in social media lately involving children and their caregivers/parents.</p> <p>This post demonstrates the vulnerability of fathers who always try their best to protect their loved ones (wives and children) but sometimes there are bad circumstances or situations beyond their control.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)</p>
5	October, 8, 2024		<p><i>Pemandangan yang selalu dirindukan waktu pulang kerja</i></p>	<p>This post portrays the emotional connection between a father and his daughter. It highlights the shared longing they experience while apart, emphasizing the joy and fulfillment of reuniting after a whole exhausting day at work. This post illustrates the deep connection and bond in a father-daughter relationship and shows the sensitive side of fathers toward their daughters.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (attractive visual)</p>
6	October, 8, 2024		<p><i>Apa saya doang yang begini? Gak mungkin ah</i></p> <p><i>#bapak2curhat</i></p>	<p>This post seeks to initiate conversations and gather fathers’ perspectives on how to parent daughters who are more sensitive and tend to become sulky toward them without clear reasons.</p> <p>This post shows that fathers have good intentions to understand how to interact with their daughters better in order to build a strong bond and relationship with them.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)</p>

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7	<p>October, 27, 2024</p>	<p><i>Sekarang saya paham kenapa bapak saya dulu jarang beli baju baru, karena untuk urusan sendiri mah kadang kagak kepikiran..</i></p>	<p>This post poses the biggest fear of a male adult figure in the family who is unable to provide for his wife and children.</p> <p>This post portrays that it is still very important for male adult figures to be looked at as the primary providers and “breadwinners” of the family.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)</p>
8	<p>October, 28, 2024</p>	<p><i>Buat menutup hari Senin, biar tidurnya berkurang tapi besok tetap semangat.</i></p> <p><i>Data yang kami dapatkan dari berkunjung ke sekolah dan dari info kenalan yang abis survey ke sekolah, mungkin akan ada tambahan biaya.</i></p>	<p>This post informs the fathers regarding the tuition fees of some private schools for the elementary level which are considered prestigious in Jakarta.</p> <p>This post uses the economic approach and is considered to be the pathway for fathers to be more involved in their children’s education.</p>	<p>Combining central (presenting data) and peripheral route (attractive visual)</p>
9	<p>October, 29, 2024</p>	<p><i>Kalo ada yg mau ditanyain lagi silakan ya, warga #bapak2sharing</i></p>	<p>This post connects fathers with a male pediatrician. They were able to pose any questions to the pediatrician concerning their newborn babies.</p> <p>Not only this post was meant to help new fathers take care of their newborns but also encouraged them to be more involved in caregiving.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (source credibility)</p>
10	<p>November, 3, 2024</p>	<p><i>Pak, bantuin isi buble teks yang di bapaknya dong, kata2 apa sih buat ekspresiin yang pas kalo kondisi begini? Kalo saya cuma terharu doangan</i></p>	<p>This post portrays the fathers’ involvement in teaching their children to ride a bike.</p> <p>Being able to ride a bike is considered to be a big milestone in both children’s and parents’ lives. This post seeks to interact with the fathers on their reactions to witnessing their children’s achievement in conquering their fear.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (attractive visual)</p>
11	<p>November, 5, 2024</p>	<p><i>Tidak mudah, tapi itulah kita.</i></p>	<p>This post demonstrates that even though it is not easy being a father who has always been portrayed as a superhero, they would still carry the huge responsibility.</p> <p>This post is considered as a support for fathers who are striving to protect their children at all costs.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)</p>

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<p>12</p>	<p>November, 11, 2024</p>		<p><i>Parenting itu kaya sekolahan, kita gak bakal berhenti belajar. Yuk pak bapak, kita bisa asal mau.</i></p> <p><i>#besokhariayah #besokharinyakita</i></p>	<p>This post presents an intimate discussion or deep talk between a father and his son. The father openly asked whether he had been a good father to him or not.</p> <p>This post portrays the loving, warm, and open side of a father. This video motivates fathers to keep on learning to be good parents to their children.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (emotional appeal)</p>
<p>13</p>	<p>November, 11, 2024</p>		<p><i>Kita bikin suasananya kaya lagi ngobrol2 sambil ngopi sama ayah, biar dalem pertanyaannya. Yang serius yah warga, besok hari ayah nih soalnya.</i></p>	<p>In welcoming Father's Day, this post encourages fathers to pose questions and build deep discussions with other members on any topics they can think of.</p> <p>This post is a teaser for product placement in collaboration with a local coffee brand.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (giveaway)</p>
<p>14</p>	<p>November, 12, 2024</p>		<p><i>Asik bener @kapalapi_id mau ngasih hadiah buat ayah kita. Warga tulis dah hal2 yang membanggakan dari ayah di kolom komen, dan jangan lupa di buka gembok akumnya yah, tungguin aja tanggal 18 Nov nanti kita umumin pemenangnya.</i></p>	<p>This is a giveaway/contest post in collaboration with a local coffee brand that encourages followers to share the proudest things about being a father.</p> <p>This post was uploaded on Father's Day.</p>	<p>Combining central (stating argument) and peripheral route (information about giveaway)</p>

<p>15</p>	<p>November, 12, 2024</p>	<p><i>Coba warga silahkan diucapin di kolom komentar terus tag temennya minimal 1 buat ikutan, jangan lupa share feed ini ke IGS juga dan tag @seabank.id & @bapak2id jangan lupa! Pasti warga juga udh punya akun SeaBank dan follow SeaBank & bapak2ID yaa! Periode ini bakal berakhir hari Minggu 18 November 2024. Nanti warga yang bakal dapet iPhone akan dimention sama @seabank.id di IG Storynya tanggal 19 November.</i></p>	<p>This is a giveaway/contest post in collaboration with a digital bank that encourages followers to share their wishes on "Father's Day", tag a friend, and reshare this post to their Instagram story.</p> <p>This post was uploaded on Father's Day.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (information about giveaway)</p>
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<p>16</p>	<p>November, 12, 2024</p>	<p><i>Kadang ayah itu salah milih kata, dan susah ngekspreiin isi hatinya, kadang terhalang gengsi, mungkin terdengar kasar dan gak empati namun percayalah kalau maksudnya baik. Kadang caranya aja yang salah. Tough Love is way of loving too..</i></p> <p><i>Abadikan kebersamaan dengan ayah melalui #vivoV40 yang dilengkapi dengan fitur #ZEISSPortraitSoPr</i></p>	<p>This post portrays how fathers aren't accustomed to expressing their true feelings verbally, therefore their expressions of love often get misunderstood by their children.</p> <p>This is paid content in collaboration with a smartphone brand.</p>	<p>Combining central (stating arguments) and peripheral route (advertisement)</p>
<p>17</p>	<p>November, 12, 2024</p>	<p><i>Selamat untuk para ayah se Indonesia! Tetaplah menjadi sosok ayah yang penuh kasih dan dirindukan</i> ❤️</p> <p><i>#bapak2id #selamathariayahna sional #barsatukitateguh</i></p>	<p>This is a greeting post on Father's Day wishing for fathers who always be the loving figure and the figure that is missed by their family.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (low cognitive effort)</p>
<p>18</p>	<p>November, 18, 2024</p>	<p><i>Selamat istirahat bareng keluarga ya, Pak</i></p> <p><i>#bapak2family #pejuangkeluarga #ayahtangguh</i></p>	<p>This post portrays the warmth and loving relationship between a father and his child. And shows each time a father comes home and is welcomed with a good hug from his child then suddenly it erases the weariness and exhaustion after working all day.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (attractive visual)</p>
<p>19</p>	<p>November, 21, 2024</p>	<p><i>Karena di balik lelahnya seorang ayah, selalu ada cinta yang nggak pernah habis</i></p> <p><i>#bapak2relationship #anakkubuahhatiku</i></p>	<p>This post shows that being a father is not just a role, but a promise to always protect their children.</p> <p>This post demonstrates fathers' who would express their love by protecting their children.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (emotional appeal)</p>

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<p>20</p> <p>November, 21, 2024</p>		<p>Anak belajar dari melihat bapaknya. Jadi teladan dulu, nasihat belakangan.</p>	<p>This post gives the fathers tips to teach responsibility to their children. While on the caption also emphasized that fathers must show good examples or model good behavior before giving pieces of advice to their children.</p>	<p>Combining central (stating arguments) and peripheral route (attractive visual)</p>
<p>21</p> <p>November 29, 2024</p>		<p>Setuju @bapak2id? 🤔🤔</p> <p>Tag & apresiasi BAPAK HEBAT itu yuk ❤️</p> <p>**</p> <p>"Ah.. kata siapa cuek bebek. Saya gak tuh"</p> <p>Bagus itu pak 😊</p> <p>Selamat.. berarti bapak termasuk BAPAK HEBAT yang struktur otaknya sudah berubah karena terus berusaha BELAJAR menjadi bapak terbaik ❤️</p>	<p>This post shares research findings which stated that males' brain structure is still the same after being a father unless they make efforts to learn and upgrade their own knowledge on parenting.</p> <p>This is a collaboration post with a local brand that sells toys & books for young children. From this post, they encourage fathers to join their private channel.</p>	<p>Combining central (stating arguments) and peripheral route (credibility of partner)</p>
<p>22</p> <p>November, 30, 2024</p>		<p>Anak-anak bikin kita ketawa, tapi matematika bikin kita jadi introspekti. Sudah berapa kali bapak pura-pura ke toilet pas mereka minta diajarin pecahan? Ngaku aja gpp pak, saya temenin..</p> <p>#bapak2analisa</p>	<p>This post portrays the role of fathers who still try to be involved in children's academic excellence whenever their children ask them, especially about their math homework, even though they're very well aware they're incapable of solving math problems.</p>	<p>Peripheral route (humor appeal)</p>

IV. RESULTS

The content posts by Bapak2ID effectively combine both central and peripheral routes in delivering their messages. This deliberate communication strategy is designed to appeal to the millennial fathers audience, encompassing a broader

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demographic with varying levels of motivation and ability to process information. This approach has proven effective, as evidenced by the high levels of engagement, including comments and replies, on almost every post. From this, we can glean valuable insights into fathers' perceptions of fatherhood.

This is further demonstrated in comments reflecting deep thought, personal experiences, and a reevaluation of traditional parenting methods. Such responses suggest deeper cognitive processing, as they emphasize the quality and relevance of the message to the individual. These interactions indicate that fathers are actively engaging with the content and thoughtfully considering how to improve their parenting approaches.

While some comments and statements are expressed in a humorous, hyperbolic, or even intimidating manner characteristic of the Bapak2ID community—they still systematically process information and carefully consider the arguments presented. The majority of testimonies also reflect a significant positive attitude shift among fathers, emphasizing their role as caregivers to their children. In terms of shared responsibilities in parenting, these fathers are progressively shifting toward a more egalitarian and involved role, taking greater responsibility for their newborns and teenagers. Additionally, there is a clear transformation in their perception of fatherhood. They are moving away from traditional views—such as being distant, strict, or solely a breadwinner—toward adapting more democratic, thoughtful, loving, and warm fatherly roles.

A. *Fatherhood is bigger than just being a provider*

A comment by @jajanan.alanin (from content no. 11) expresses a deeper reflection on the traditional notion of being a father. It encourages fathers to think critically about the broader responsibilities they hold in shaping their children's lives. This reflection requires more cognitive effort as it reminds fathers to consider their active role in nurturing, guiding, and educating their children, which goes beyond being the sole provider.

Reply 1:

Betul banget pak. Saya kira dulu tugas jadi bapak tuh cuma 'nyari nafkah doang', rupanya lebih dari sekedar itu ? (That's right, sir. I thought that the job of a father was only to 'earn a living', apparently it's more than just that 🙏).

This comment by @pop_benk (from content no. 5) reflects deeper contemplation, emphasizing that these heartfelt moments are fleeting, as children will eventually outgrow them. It serves as a reminder for fathers to cherish these times while they last, fostering a lasting appreciation of their role in their family's life.

Reply 2:

One of the best moments ever. Enjoy it while we can, because it won't last for long Pak- Bapak

B. *Fathers acknowledge in suppressing their feelings & emotions*

This comment by @betyouwill234 was referring from content no. 14. The user acknowledges a societal paradox for men to suppress their emotions, especially when it comes to expressing vulnerability, making it difficult for them to openly share their feelings or struggles. It highlights their feelings and speaks to a deeper reflection on the role of fathers in family life. It encourages thoughtfulness about the often-unsung emotional labor that fathers perform, urging others to recognize and appreciate the unspoken efforts and sacrifices.

Yes.. This video represents all of father in the world [...] because a father always do not talk [...]

C. *Fathers as role model*

A comment by @gatot_apu83 (from content no. 4) highlights the vital role of fathers in serving as role models and shaping their children's character, particularly in fostering good morals and empathy. By emphasizing the importance of leading by example, the statement highlights the father's influence on a child's development, both emotionally and ethically. It reflects the belief that children learn values not just through instruction but also through observing their parents' behavior.

Sangat penting perang orangtua khususnya BAPAK, untuk mencontohkan dan membentuk karakter anak yg berakhlak baik n punya empati (It is very important for parents, especially fathers, to set an example and shape the character of children who have good morals and empathy).

D. *Fathers are perceived as being open, reflective, and willing to learn*

A comment by @triunt (from content no. 1) highlights the importance of fostering open communication between parents and children, emphasizing the central route of engagement in parenting. By actively listening and encouraging children to share their thoughts and experiences, parents can build trust and create a safe space for dialogue.

Reply 1:

Itu pertanda bagus, karena si anak terbuka, denger baik2 jangan sampai anak kapok cerita Pak, tar kalo dia sudah remaja, sangat melegakan sekali punya anak yang mau cerita tentang relasinya dengan lawan jenis, tinggal pinter2nya kita mengarahkan tanpa bikin anak kapok cerita 🧡 🌟 (That's a positive sign, as it shows the child is open. Listen carefully to ensure the child doesn't feel discouraged from sharing. As they grow into their teenage years, it will be a great relief to have a child who is willing to discuss their relationships with the opposite sex. The key lies in how wisely we guide them without discouraging their openness 🙌🏻)

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The statement by @fauzanharizbinmuchlishmuhammad (from content no. 16) urges fathers to critically analyze their behavior and reflect on their shortcomings and advocates for continuous self-improvement, personal reflection, and correction of wrongdoings, which points to a deeper and more lasting change in attitude.

Reply 2:

Setiap ada kekurangan, maka kiranya untuk mengkoreksi dan instropeksi. Janganlah terus menormalisasikan hal yang kurang, bahkan salah. Intinya, kalimat baik haruslah diterapkan dengan cara yang baik, stop katakan : "saya mulutnya (omongannya) memang kasar, tapi hati lembut". Totally wrong!" (Every time there is a shortcoming, it serves as an opportunity to correct and self-reflect. Do not continue to normalize or justify shortcomings, especially when they are wrong. The key is to apply good intentions and words in a good way. Stop saying, "My words may be harsh, but my heart is soft." That mindset is completely wrong!").

The user @rigusa89 (from content no. 16) suggest that fathers need to learn better communication. It invites deeper reflection on how miscommunication can lead to misunderstandings, missed connections, and delayed emotional bonding with children. The recommendation challenges fathers to overcome societal stereotypes of emotional restraint and to actively develop skills for open dialogue with their children.

Reply 3:

Berarti bapak2 harus belajar komunikasi yg lebih baik, jd hal kyk gini biar ga terulang lg. Jgn krn gengsi, ga bs ekspresif, lalu meminta anak untuk memaklumi. Yg ada anaknya sadarnya telat kalo ternyata maksudnya bkn 'gitu.' (This means fathers need to learn better communication to prevent such misunderstandings. Don't be embarrassed or afraid to express yourself, and don't expect children to understand on their own. Otherwise, children might only realize too late that things weren't meant to be 'like that.')

A comment by @zyidaan (from content no. 2) portrays fathers as figures who are willing to learn new knowledge, adopt the idea, and then turn it into action, showing a strong commitment on being a good father to their children.

Reply 4:

Membantu banget nih infonya jadi semangat mau praktekin biar bayinya bisa nyaman seperti ini (This information is incredibly helpful, and I'm excited to put it into practice to ensure my baby feels comfortable like this).

E. Fathers adopt an egalitarian role in parenting

This comment by @bayuraharjo7 (from content no. 2) reflects the importance of shared responsibility in parenting, emphasizing that both parents, regardless of gender, should equally contribute to the care and upbringing of their children. It challenges traditional gender roles, where caregiving has historically been viewed as primarily the mother's responsibility. Reminding fathers that they "made them together," highlights the collaborative parenting (co-parenting) or adopting egalitarian approach in parenting and the mutual duty both parents have in nurturing and caring for their children.

Pack,momongna berdua yaa Kan bikinnya berdua.. (Dads, take care of your children together, since you made them together...)

F. Fathers reinvent their own parenting style

This statement by @nagrasd (from content no. 2) engages the central route because it reflects a move toward more modern, flexible parenting approaches and away from rigid, traditional methods. By stating that they focus on "natural theories" rather than adhering strictly to conventional advice, he emphasizes a personalized, adaptive approach to parenting, one that considers the child's individual needs and developmental stages rather than relying on one-size-fits-all rules.

Reply 1:

Kalo Saya sm Istri pada intinya ngerawat Bayi (Anak) lebih balik ke teori alamiahnya, udah ga begitu mentingin apa kata Emak Babe yang kadang "Kudu gini nih, Kudu gitu tuh [...]" (My wife and I basically take care of babies (children) based on natural theories, no longer worrying about traditional advice like 'It has to be like this, it has to be like that' [...])

The deeper aspect of this comment by @steffen_756 (from content number 11) involves reflection on fatherhood and the desire to change the course of their own parenting to ensure a better experience for their child. By actively seeking advice and guidance, he is encouraging reflection and critical thinking about what it means to be a good father. The mention of wanting to avoid the same experiences for their child invites the audience to consider the qualities and actions that contribute to positive father-child relationships and the importance of conscious, active parenting.

Reply 2:

Saya gk pernah ngerasa hebatnya seorang ayah... Tapi saya gk mau anak saya juga begitu.. tolong nasihat dan arahannya pak 🙏 (I've never felt the greatness of a father, but I don't want my child to experience the same thing. Please give me advice and guidance, sir 🙏).

G. Fathers acknowledge the importance of mental health & good education

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A comment by @td889_ (from content no. 2) encourages thoughtful reflection on the impact of mental health on parenting and highlights the necessity of being informed about the challenges of parenthood. By focusing on the deeper, more serious aspects of parenting—such as mental health awareness and early education—this statement motivates new parents to engage with information that could help them navigate difficult emotional experiences and improve their well-being, ultimately fostering more responsible, aware, and prepared parenting.

Reply 1:

[...] tapi bagus ini informasi buat new parenting biar gada pembunuhan anak akibat baby blues, dsb. Kita bisa belajar dari dini. ([...] but this is good information for new parents so there are no child murders due to baby blues. We can learn from an early age.)

The idea of education being a long-term investment for a child's future encourages deeper reflection in @fauzibaru's comment (from content no. 8). It appeals to the logical and rational side of the audience, prompting them to consider the importance of quality education as a foundation for their children's future success. It invites the audience to think critically about the long-term benefits of investing in education, including financial sacrifices and the value of preparing children for adulthood.

Reply 2:

Kalo saya punya uang sebanyak itupun akan saya sekolahkan anak saya disana, pendidikan adalah investasi untuk bekal anak di masa dewasa. (If I had that much money, I would send my child to school there, as education is an investment in a child's future). However, a comment by @zainalfurqon (from content no. 8) give another perspective to think critically about how parents need to also contribute to their child's moral and spiritual growth through home education by instilling religious values and practices.

Reply 3:

Dan yang terpenting adalah, pendidikan dari dalam rumah khususnya dari kedua orang tuanya langsung. Terutama untuk pendidikan agama [...] (And the most important thing is education from within the home, especially from both parents directly. This is particularly true for religious education [...]).

G. Fathers' emotional and mental growth

The comment by @dimas666one (from content no. 3) reflects a profound transformation in perspective that often accompanies fatherhood, where personal priorities shift toward a focus on family well-being and responsibility. It expresses a significant departure from self-centered thinking, emphasizing a deep commitment to ensuring his wife and children's happiness and a decent standard of living, even at the expense of his own needs and desires.

Reply 1:

Yg saya rasain sekarang dulu sebelum nikah sebelum punya anak masih belum terfikir sejauh ini, tapi sesudah punya anak semua fikiran saya ke egoisan saya untuk diri sendiri hilang ntah kemana. [...] (What I feel now is that before I got married before I had children, I still didn't think this far, but after having children all my thoughts of my selfishness for myself disappeared who knows where. [...]).

Then a comment by @yazid.busthami (from content no.1) suggests a more thoughtful and nurturing perspective, reflecting a father who guides with wisdom and emphasizes acknowledging and managing emotions responsibly. It demonstrates a thoughtful reflection on emotions and responsibilities. This advice promotes self-awareness and prioritizes long-term values over immediate reactions:

Reply 2:

Well, rasa suka itu datangnya gak bisa dibuat-buat, ia datang dari Allah. Tapi, bagaimana kita mengungkapkan perasaan suka itu yang berada di tanggung jawab kita. Saat ini, kalau kamu disukai, cukup bilang terima kasih dulu saja. Karena kita juga gak bisa buat dia gak suka lagi sama kita. Bilang "Kita masih kecil, kita fokus belajar saja [...] (Feelings of liking come from Allah and cannot be faked. However, how we express them is our responsibility. If someone expresses interest in you, thank them politely and remind them to focus on growth and studies for now [...])

I. Fathers are the protectors of their children (especially daughters)

Many fathers interpret their role as the primary figure in protecting their family, especially safeguarding their daughters from potential harm or undesirable influences from boys or other male figures besides them. This sentiment is often expressed in a hyperbolic and intimidating manner, characteristic of the Bapak2ID community's cultural humor, where underlying concerns are masked as jokes

A comment by @hendy_intermezzo (from content no. 1) questions about practical skills and family background rely on

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external markers of competence and suitability, reflecting a stereotypical approach to assessing character.

Reply 1:

Dia kerja dimana?bisa pasang gas?bisa ganti ban mobil bocor?anaknya siapa?ooh..bapak dia kerjanya apa? (Where does he work? Can he install cooking gas? Can he change a flat tire? Who is his father? Ooh.. what does his father do for a living?)

Anecdotal comments by @jasadesainkitchen (content no. 2) on putting down newborn babies to sleep employ humor in highlighting practical tips and solutions.

Reply 2:

Bisa juga pake kipas angin Miyako yang sedeng juga ampuh ngeblock segala macem suara pak,kipasnya arahkan ke dinding agak jauh dari bayi, suara tikus shift malam, knalpot akamsi, komentator voli rt sebelah, semuanya kalah sama suara kipas (The sound of a Miyako fan defeats everything: night shift mice, muffler sound from the neighbours motorbike, volleyball commentators from the next RT, all gone!)

Not only through humor, the emotional and reassuring tone of @advent_wijaya's message (from content no.1) emphasizes the emotional bond and intrinsic values in the father-daughter relationship. It conveys a deeply personal and reflective perspective, focusing on the father's role as the first source of love, support, and happiness in his daughter's life. It also shows the encouragement of trust toward the father as her primary male figure. This comment surely negates the missing father figure in one child's life that would potentially lead to a fatherless phenomenon.

Reply 3:

Sebelum orang itu suka kamu, Papah yg terlebih dulu menyukaimu, Sebelum orang itu sayang sama kamu, Papah yg terlebih dahulu menyayangi mu, Jika rasa suka orang lain membuat mu bahagia, Papah akan lakukan hal-hal yg lebih baik dari dia lakukan untuk membuat mu merasa jauh lebih bahagia dari yg orang lain itu lakukan (Before anyone else likes you, Daddy liked you first. Before anyone else loves you, Daddy loved you first. If others make you happy, Daddy will do even more to ensure your happiness.)

J. Fathers are loving, attentive, and warm

A comment by @d.a.n._ichwal (from content no. 5) highlights the dual emotional and physical challenges faced by fathers who work outside the home. It acknowledges the perseverance required of fathers to balance work responsibilities with family life while also celebrating the joy and motivation that family provides.

Reply 1:

Momen paling menghilangkan penat sepulang kerja ya itu disambut anak anak dan istri, semangat terus para bapak yang berjuang di luar rumah (The moment that best relieves fatigue after work is being greeted by one's children and wife. Keep up the spirit up, dads, as you continue to strive outside the home.)

The comment by @walimahendra_ portrays (content no. 5) that the act of bringing snacks serves as a simple act of love and affection .

Reply 2:

Bawa katong kresek isi jajan 😊 (Bring a plastic bag filled with snacks 😊).

V. CONCLUSIONS

From this research, it is evident that the existence of a digital reference group such as Bapak2ID contributes to these paradigm shifts, where the male figure is also regarded as an equal primary caregiver alongside mothers. This is evidenced by the majority of followers, who are millennial fathers inclined to adopt the concept of egalitarian parenting, becoming more involved in every aspect of their children's lives, including education, relationships, and mental health. They are also open to the idea of a democratic or authoritative parenting style and are willing to incorporate these approaches into their personal lives.

However, certain core values remain deeply ingrained, such as the perception of fathers as the protectors of their family and the primary breadwinners. This duality highlights the evolving role of modern fathers, balancing traditional expectations with a more active and inclusive approach to parenting.

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